

two stable states at 160° and 185° are obtained.
 weight of the sample taken = 140 mg.
 weight loss at 160° = 14 mg.
 weight loss at 185° = 75 mg.
 Found : weight loss at 160° = 10%
 weight loss at 185° = 52.9%
 Net weight loss between two stable states = 42.9%.

Calculated weight loss for the final composition $K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$ = 44%.

In case of $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$, 2 oxine only one stable state at 240° is obtained.

weight of the sample taken = 150 mg.
 weight loss at 240° = 64 mg.

Found : weight loss at 240° = 42.7%.

Calculated weight loss for the final composition $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ = 46%

$K_4[Fe(CN)_6] \cdot 2 \text{ oxine} \rightarrow K_4[Fe(CN)_6] + 2 \text{ oxine} \dots (1)$
 $K_3[Fe(CN)_6] \cdot 2 \text{ oxine} \rightarrow K_3[Fe(CN)_6] + 2 \text{ oxine} \dots (2)$

Magnetic susceptibility measurements :

Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made in Gouy balance at 24°. The compound $K_4[Fe(CN)_6] \cdot 2 \text{ oxine}$ is diamagnetic (molar susceptibility λ_M (corrected) = $-86.95 \times 10^{-6} / \text{g atom}$). The compound $K_3[Fe(CN)_6] \cdot 2 \text{ oxine}$ (with diamagnetic correction) has $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.839 \times (\lambda_M \times T)^{1/2} = 2.2 \text{ B. M.}$

Infra-red spectra were taken in Perkin Elmer Infra-red spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. Main bands with assignments are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Compounds	Infra-red absorption bands (in cm^{-1})	Assignments
1. $K_4[Fe(CN)_6] \cdot 2 \text{ oxine}$	570s, 700w, 750m, 820s, 1090s, 1200vw, 1300s, 1390m, 1550m, 1600s, 1630w, 2120vs, 2900-3100wb.	$\nu_{\text{CN}^-} = 2120$
2. $K_3[Fe(CN)_6] \cdot 2 \text{ oxine}$	570vw, 750m, 820s, 880m, 1050w, 1090s, 1260vw, 1300s, 1390w, 1550m, 1600s, 2100s, 2900-3100wb.	$\nu_{\text{CN}^-} = 2100$

Reflectance spectra of compounds in solid state were taken in Hilger UVISPEK in paraffin base. Main bands with intensities are given Table 2.

TABLE 2

Compounds	ν in cm^{-1}	Intensity
1. $K_4[Fe(CN)_6] \cdot 2 \text{ oxine}$	12500	w
	14700	w
	24400	m
2. $K_3[Fe(CN)_6] \cdot 2 \text{ oxine}$	13700	w
	16400	m
	19200	m
	22500	sh

m=medium ; w=weak ; s=strong ; sh=shoulder , v=very , b=broad.

References

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Chemical Examination of *Premna integrifolia* Linn

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PREMNA integrifolia Linn (N.O. *Verbenaceae*) is of a great value in Ayurvedic medicine. The decoction of the root is used for liver complaints, of the plant in rheumatism and neuralgia and, of leaves in cold and fever¹. Search in literature has shown that this plant had not been examined for its crystalline principles. In the present investigation, the leaves and the stem bark have been examined.

The air dried leaves (2 Kg.) were extracted successively with *n*-hexane and ether. The hexane extract gave a dark green mass (3 gm). It did not contain any alkali solubles. So it was adsorbed over neutral alumina and eluted in succession with *n*-hexane (2 litres), and benzene (2 litres). The *n*-hexane eluate gave a yellow oil (1 gm) while the benzene eluate gave a white solid (1.5 gm), crystallizing from methanol as colourless needles [m. p. 136-138° : (α)_D²⁰ -36°]. The solid gave positive Libermann-Burchard test for sterols and was identified as β -sitosterol (mmp and IR). The ether extract also gave a dark green mass (1 gm) which on chromatography over alumina (eluted with benzene) gave β -sitosterol acetate (0.75 gm), crystallized from methanol as colourless needles m. p. 126-127° : (α)_D²⁰ -36°.

The ether extract of the stem-bark furnished only β -sitosterol while the *n*-hexane extract of the same yielded β -sitosterol and betulin. The latter crystallised from methanol in needles m. p. 248-250° (lit. 255°)² (α)_D¹⁹ +19° (CHCl_3) ; diacetate, m. p. 210-212° ; IR : 885 and 1653 cm^{-1} (= CH_2), PMR : 5.3 τ (2H, b.S, = CH_2). In each case the identity has been established by direct comparison with the respective authentic samples.

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